

Perspective

An eco-epidemiological framework for reducing the abundance of mosquito vectors in urban water bodies: A case study of Jakkur Lake in Bengaluru, India

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Abstract

Rapid urbanization and climate variability reshape the hydrological cycles of urban ecosystems, creating conditions that can amplify the spread of vector-borne diseases such as dengue. In Indian megacities like Bengaluru, where impermeable surfaces and water retention contribute to seasonal vector proliferation, current strategies for mosquito control remain fragmented and reactive. The aim of this perspective is to explore how the current water management practices can be used to support ecological restoration and vector control, thereby reducing the risk of mosquito-borne diseases in wetland environments. To address this, this perspective proposes an integrated framework that applies One Health principles to operationalize Nature-based Solutions for reducing mosquito vector proliferation and improving water management in cities. We outline four key contributions: (1) principles of Water Sensitive Urban Design in Sponge Cities for mitigating vector habitats, (2) insights into urban water management and dengue ecology at Bengaluru's Jakkur Lake site, (3) a case study as a model for operationalizing Nature-based Solutions, and (4) a roadmap for implementing a One Health approach that integrates human, urban, and broader ecological health.

Keywords: One Health; Dengue; Water-sensitive Urban Design; Nature-based Solutions; Wetlands; Infectious Diseases; Climate Change Adaptation.

1. Introduction

Dengue is the single most important mosquito-borne viral illness globally [1]. Due to its significant economic and societal impacts, reducing the mosquito-borne disease burden in India is essential for achieving sustainable development [2]. Dengue, the world's fastest-growing vector-borne disease, has experienced a 30-fold increase in global incidence over the past 50 years, with half of the world's population currently at risk of contracting the disease, placing immense pressure on public health systems [3]. Symptoms of dengue range from a mild fever to severe conditions such as dengue hemorrhagic fever and dengue shock syndrome, which can be fatal [1]. Dengue has led to numerous deaths, and is particularly rampant during flood events in megacities such as Bengaluru, which bears more than half of the disease burden within the state of Karnataka [4]. As of mid-2024, Bengaluru reported 2,830 dengue cases, marking a 37% increase compared to the same period in 2023, and over 200% increase since 2022 [5, 6].

In India, human-induced environmental changes, including rapid, unplanned urbanization, deforestation, population growth, underdeveloped stormwater drainage systems, and inadequate waste and sanitation services, create conditions highly conducive to mosquito proliferation, escalating the transmission of dengue [7–9]. The causative agent of dengue, a *Flavivirus*, is transmitted from one person to another by female mosquitoes of the genus *Aedes*, primarily *Ae. aegypti* and *Ae. Albopictus* [10]. Stagnant water in urban environments often constitutes breeding grounds for larval growth leading to seasonal disease outbreaks [11]. Currently, with no antiviral therapy or affordable and safe vaccine available in low-income settings like India, combating dengue primarily relies on vector control, such as insecticides [12, 13]. While these strategies can reduce mosquito populations in the short term, they have also been associated with the elimination of natural predators, including but not limited to odonates, beetles, and fishes, as well as the development of insecticide resistance, resulting in ecological imbalance and diminishing their long-term effectiveness [12, 14–17].

2. Research gaps

Recognizing the escalating pressures of climate variability and rapid urbanization on public health, our study proposes a more holistic approach to Nature-based Solutions as integral components within adaptive urban environmental management strategies. Numerous cities are already exploring

Nature-based Solutions for urban challenges in their climate adaptation plans and resilience measures [18]. Nature-based solutions, such as constructed wetlands, green roofs, and rain gardens, offer a transformative approach to addressing the ecological drivers of vector proliferation while providing co-benefits, such as biodiversity enhancement, aquifer recharge, and flood mitigation [19, 20]. Yet, governance and implementation gaps are evident in the lack of holistic frameworks connecting ecological restoration with public health, compounded by a lack of enforcement of building codes and corporate social responsibility guidelines that would otherwise protect surrounding ecosystems from urban expansion [21].

Extensive evidence in the literature shows that constructed wetlands can inadvertently provide breeding habitats for mosquito vectors, undermining the importance of careful planning and implementation [19, 20, 22–24]. Meanwhile, there is a lack of evidence-based strategies that rigorously integrate water management with vector control, and an absence of continuous, systematic data collection on vector dynamics, water quality, biodiversity, and community health outcomes in urban wetland systems [25]. A fundamental challenge lies in aligning the maintenance and upkeep of urban hydrological ecosystems, with evolving pressures of urbanisation and climate change. This raises the question of how Nature-based Solutions can be operationalised to support urban development while minimizing ecological and public health risk.

Dengue mosquitoes primarily breed in small collections of clean water, such as containers, flower pots, discarded tires, and water storage systems [25]. Although *Ae. aegypti* tend to prefer fresh, clean stagnant waters, they can adapt to new ecological niches and breed in polluted water bodies, such as turbid wetlands, as well [26]. Hence, urban flooding in Bengaluru especially from heavy monsoon rainfall has amplified vector proliferation [4, 25, 27, 28]. Despite the well-documented role of urban water governance in shaping vector populations, evidence-based strategies that integrate water management with vector control remain underexplored [29, 30]. This gap points to a critical need for urban planning approaches that treat water not only as an engineering challenge, but as a shared ecological and public health resource.

3. Proposed approach for a holistic framework

Nature-based Solutions, particularly those that integrate urban water management with ecosystem restoration, offer a promising pathway by leveraging ecological processes to strengthen a system's capacity to deal with interconnected challenges. In this context, they contribute to more holistic approaches to climate change adaptation and resilience. **Among these, Water Sensitive Urban Design (WSUD) and the Sponge City concept represent key Nature-based Solutions frameworks** that embed hydrological functions within urban landscapes.

WSUD is a planning approach that integrates ecological principles into the management of urban water systems to address the hydrological, environmental, and social challenges posed by urbanization [31, 32]. It is characterized by a shift from rapid drainage towards the retention, infiltration, and reuse of water close to its source. As a Nature-based Solutions approach, WSUD employs interventions such as bioswales, green roofs, constructed wetlands, and permeable pavements to maintain or restore the natural water cycle within urban landscapes [33].

A key strength of WSUD is its adaptability to site-specific hydrological and ecological conditions. By aligning with Nature-based Solutions principles, WSUD enhances biodiversity and delivers co-benefits such as microclimate regulation [34–36]. Importantly, these interventions can also influence public health by altering the availability, persistence, and spatial distribution of standing water, which are key determinants of mosquito breeding habitats.

While WSUD has predominantly been applied for flood mitigation, its potential to contribute to the management of mosquito-borne disease risk, remains underexplored [32]. In rapidly urbanising settings such as Bengaluru city, the expansion of impermeable surfaces disrupts infiltration, and promotes seasonal flooding and water stagnation, conditions that facilitate mosquito proliferation [29]. The effectiveness of WSUD in such contexts depends on appropriate design and maintenance, as poorly maintained systems may inadvertently create conditions conducive to mosquito breeding [29, 30, 37].

While WSUD provides a planning a design framework, the Sponge City concept represents a more targeted and scalable type of Nature-based Solution, particularly suited to cities facing intense seasonal rainfall and infrastructure strain, such as Bengaluru and other megacities in India. Originally developed in China, the concept envisions cities functioning like sponges, absorbing rainwater during wet periods and

releasing it gradually through a network of decentralized green infrastructure [36]. The main characteristics of Sponge Cities include the use of interventions such as rain gardens, urban wetlands, and retention basins. These systems collectively reduce runoff, recharge groundwater, and mitigate the formation of stagnant water bodies that favor mosquito breeding. By restoring urban hydrology and reducing environmental risks, Sponge Cities demonstrate how Nature-based Solutions can be operationalized to simultaneously support climate adaptation and vector control.

In Bengaluru, combining WSUD principles with Sponge City strategies presents a promising opportunity to regulate urban hydrology and address both flooding and mosquito vector risks [8]. By reducing stagnant water through improved absorption, retainment, and reuse of water, they can help minimize breeding grounds for mosquitoes while enhancing urban resilience to climate-related challenges [35, 36]. Additionally, they can also help mitigate challenges associated with rapid urbanization, such as impermeable surfaces and urban heat island effects, but can simultaneously constitute breeding habitats, increasing the risk of vector-borne diseases [8, 33].

In this perspective, we draw on the case study of Jakkur Lake in Bengaluru city , to illustrate how WSUD principles can be adapted to support Sponge City functions within urban contexts. This case study provides a practical basis for how Nature-based Solutions can be operationalised to support healthier urban hydrological systems and ecosystems. **By aligning these principles within the One Health framework, we identify opportunities to mobilize stakeholders, and expand traditional wetland management solutions.** Through this we aim to propose an integrated eco-epidemiological framework to explore how current water management strategies could support ecological restoration and vector control.

4. Urban water management and mosquito vectors in Bengaluru city, India

Bengaluru's urban water management systems illustrate complex interactions between urbanization, infrastructure development, and public health risks [15, 33]. Historically connected lakes and drainage systems have over time become fragmented or encroached upon by unsupervised urban growth [38, 39]. Thus, during Bengaluru's monsoon season, inadequate drainage has exacerbated urban flooding, and has led to prolonged pooling of water in residential and commercial areas, providing ideal conditions for mosquitobreeding [4, 10, 30, 43]. Furthermore, poorly managed construction waste has further

exacerbated this problem by clogging drains and creating microhabitats for mosquito breeding in discarded items such as tires, containers, and debris [25,44]. Beyond shortcomings in drainage infrastructure, water storage practices in Bengaluru also pose a significant challenge. In response to seasonal water scarcity, many households rely on rooftop tanks or containers for water storage [45]. While these systems provide a critical resource for urban residents, their improper maintenance has turned them into mosquito breeding sites [46]. Mosquito breeding in Bengaluru has also been influenced by the socio-economic disparities across the city. In low-income neighborhoods, inadequate waste disposal and poor housing conditions have contributed disproportionately to the risk of mosquito proliferation making these communities highly vulnerable to the health impacts of diseases like dengue [9, 47]. Population growth and urban expansion in Bengaluru has significantly increased the housing demand and infrastructure development. This is often associated with encroaching upon natural mosquito predators, such as dragonflies and birds, leading to deregulated mosquito population growth [49]. While efforts have been made to restore parts of Bengaluru's hydrological infrastructure, such as its network of lakes and wetlands, these projects have lacked integrated public health outcomes in their design and operation [50]. Furthermore, unmonitored waste disposal into urban lakes has turned many water bodies into breeding grounds rather than ecological assets [25]. This highlights the absence of holistic frameworks connecting ecological restoration with vector control and sustainable urban water management [31]. To illustrate how such integration can be achieved in practice, we examined the case of Jakkur lake in Bengaluru. This lake was selected as it provided a relevant example of how WSUD principles could potentially be implemented through Nature-based Solutions to address the dual challenges of vector breeding habitat reduction and sustainable urban water management. The case study included two field observations of the lake in August 2023, complemented by semi-structured interviews with local experts (n=5) and targeted review of the relevant literature. These inputs were synthesised through a SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats) analysis, which informed the insights presented in this perspective.

4.1. Study site description

Jakkur lake spans 160 acres, and is one of the largest water bodies in northern Bengaluru, functioning as both a traditional lake and a site incorporating constructed wetland features as part of its restoration [50].

Historically, the lake was part of Bengaluru's extensive network of water bodies, serving as rainwater catchment systems, mitigating urban floods while supporting irrigation and biodiversity [33]. Until today, it constitutes a critical ecological and hydrological asset for the surrounding urban area and is frequently cited as one of the relatively well-maintained and effectively governed lake systems in the city, based on community and stakeholder perceptions [51, 52]. However, rapid urbanization, coupled with insufficient infrastructure and governance, has led to widespread degradation of many lakes, including Jakkur, with many water bodies becoming hotspots for mosquito breeding and pollution, threatening their ecological and public health roles [53]. Nevertheless, during recent restoration efforts at Jakkur Lake, certain WSUD principles have already been implemented, with an aim to enhance water quality, reduce vector habitats, and improve ecosystem resilience [40]. Some of these restorations have been discussed in the sections below.

Figure 1. Jakkur Lake wetland with inflow from the adjacent sewage treatment plant (Photo by E. Donderer).

As part of its ecological restoration, Jakkur lake includes a constructed wetland and algal pond upstream, where treated water from an adjacent sewage treatment plant is filtered before entering the

lake (Fig. 1) [51, 52]. This dual-purpose system allows the lake to function as a traditional water reservoir and as a managed wetland, providing additional benefits such as water quality improvement and urban drainage [54]. The lake restoration initiative has further engaged local communities through clean-up activities, school programs, such as so-called Living Labs and public awareness initiatives, fostering local ownership and improving the understanding of the importance of maintaining water ecosystems to prevent vector proliferation (Fig. 2) [38, 40, 56]. The outdoor learning center at the lake (Fig. 2), serves as a Living Lab for school programs and community education on water ecosystems and governance, and is central to these efforts. It also adds value as a medicinal plant garden, further enriching its educational offerings. Despite its capacities for community engagement and governance, this center currently relies entirely on grassroots efforts for its sustained operation. Furthermore, its current educational focus does not explore the intricate interplay of risk and opportunity through Nature-based Solutions, particularly concerning public health.

Figure 2. Outdoor learning center at Jakkur Lake, serving as a Living Lab for school programs and community education on water ecosystems and governance (Photo by E. Donderer).

During a site visit, direct observation of the drainage channel highlighted both the challenges and resilience of this system (Fig. 1). While areas of untreated overflow and significant plastic pollutant accumulation were noted along the channel, indicating potential bypass events or incomplete filtration requiring further investigation, we also observed robust, healthy vegetation growth within the channel (Fig. 1). Furthermore, only a few sections of the channel exhibited stagnant conditions, suggesting variable flow dynamics and localized self-purification capacity.

4.2. SWOT Analysis

Five local expert interviews, site visits and a purposive literature review helped us identify weaknesses, and threats in the Jakkur lake wetland system that can help us leverage existing strengths to formulate opportunities for a Nature-based Solutions approach tailored to public health concerns surrounding urban wetlands. By aligning the weaknesses, threats, strengths, and opportunities for reduced mosquito breeding at Jakkur Lake, we find that enhanced water absorption and controlled drainage, could help prevent the accumulation of stagnant water and subsequent breeding sites [57].

First, gaps in maintenance, monitoring, and governance were noted by experts as a weakness of the site [58]. For example, during our visit, residents and local researchers reported untreated sewage overflow from the sewage treatment plant during peak capacity periods [55]. Additionally, we found that surrounding construction projects had further increased flood risks by sealing natural drainage channels [51, 54]. The ongoing sewage overflow and recurring monsoon floods continue to threaten water quality and disrupt the ecological balance of local water bodies such as Jakkur Lake [40, 54]. Hence, continuous data collection on vector dynamics regarding water quality, populations, and community health outcomes is essential to assess the effectiveness of Nature-based Solutions interventions, but remains absent at Jakkur Lake and similar sites [38, 45]. Moreover, it is necessary to maintain water flow and control water retention times in containers to less than 24–30 hours in order to disrupt the mosquito life cycle [11].

Regular sediment removal, vegetation management, and waste clearance are crucial to maintain the ecological health of the wetland and prevent unintended breeding habitats, but currently lack oversight (Fig. 3-4). Despite the presence of explicit "Do Not Litter" signage, solid waste accumulation at the Jakkur Lake site remains a pervasive issue. The juxtaposition of current communication strategies for environmental protection and the persistent presence of pollution highlights a significant challenge in

community adherence and enforcement, particularly given the absence of systematic data on the sources and composition of this litter. Understanding the origins of this waste, whether from residents, market waste, or upstream influxes, is critical for developing targeted and effective waste management strategies beyond mere signage.

Figure 3. “Do not litter” signage at the Jakkur Lake site (Photo by E. Donderer).

Second, a threat to the effectiveness of Nature-based Solutions in reducing abundance of mosquito vectors lies in the human perception of nature itself. Experts note maintenance as a vital success factor which in turn depends on the approaches and philosophies deployed by local agencies towards restoration of blue green infrastructure and the interactions between communities and their surrounding ecosystems. In Bengaluru, once a lake restoration project is approved, the Bruhat Bengaluru Mahanagara Palike (BBMP), the administrative body responsible for civic amenities and some infrastructural assets, follows a checklist of activities [59]. First, the lake is dredged, increasing its depth, and converting it into a bowl shape [60]. Second, shoreline vegetation is removed, even though research

shows that such vegetation is crucial for maintaining the ecological health of the lake and helps create species balance, which prevents the growth of blue-green algae [59]. Third, diversion channels are constructed that, in addition to preventing the entry of raw sewage, also stop rainwater and secondary treated water from entering the lake. These interventions create stagnant conditions at the lake, increasing the hydraulic retention time of water and providing an ideal habitat for mosquito breeding [60].

Figure 4. Evidence of solid waste at the Jakkur Lake site during a visit in August 2023 (Photo by E. Donderer).

Therefore, the notion that Nature-based Solutions are self-regulating or inherently effective simply because they are natural overlooks the complexities of system health and the sociocultural dimensions of ecological interventions [53]. In Bengaluru, green and blue spaces are often designed with a highly manicured, neocolonial aesthetic, prioritizing symmetry and control over ecological function [61]. This approach, while visually appealing, frequently neglects the incorporation of native vegetation and fails to attract biodiversity, ultimately reducing the ecological resilience of these spaces [38]. Even more, the favoring of manicured, ornamental green public spaces frequently clashes with the more dynamic, and at times less tidy appearances of ecologically functional Nature-based Solutions designs. This aesthetic preference, often rooted in historical perceptions and societal norms, can lead to a misperception of

nature's role in urban environments, limiting public acceptance and the sustained maintenance of solutions vital for public health. For instance, the very features of a wetland that enhance biodiversity and facilitate vector predation, such as emergent vegetation, might be perceived as unkempt or problematic if the dominant aesthetic promotes sterile, manicured landscapes.

Third, these challenges highlight the importance of sustained community engagement and multi-stakeholder collaboration [29]. Notable as a strength, the active involvement of local communities in lake management has been a cornerstone of Jakkur Lake's restoration, few other lake sites offer such access and are more often fenced and inaccessible to the public [40]. Community watchdogs play an important role in providing information and may benefit from digital tools to help collect georeferenced data on sites that require attention and maintenance [44]. For instance, government agencies may launch citizen science programs to monitor water quality, vegetation cover, and facilitate active mosquito surveillance through adult trapping methods and larval collections [53]. Integrating dengue awareness programs into educational efforts remains an untapped opportunity. Public events, school programs, and the existing living lab programs at Jakkur Lake could be steered toward raising awareness about reducing mosquito breeding habitats while fostering environmental stewardship.

Neglecting sociocultural dimensions critically limits Nature-based Solutions success. Opportunities, therefore, lie in fostering culturally resonant and ecologically functional Nature-based Solutions designs that bridge this perceptual gap. This requires engaging local communities not merely as beneficiaries, but as co-designers and stewards, integrating traditional ecological knowledge and local preferences into the planning process [29, 62]. Community insights into local topography, hydrology, vegetation, and water sources are critical, with further merit lying in the exploration of the religious significance of certain water bodies or tree species that can shape how diverse communities interact with, identify themselves, and maintain these spaces [56]. Jakkur Lake, which serves both ecological and recreational purposes, illustrates the importance of integrating anthropological elements into Nature-based Solutions design [52]. Local festivals, cultural events, and rituals held around the lake foster a sense of ownership and stewardship among residents, while contact with the natural environment offers a range of co-benefits for human health, yet these interactions also pose challenges [2]. For example, the accumulation of waste during large gatherings can contribute to waterlogging and mosquito breeding if

not managed effectively [7]. The effective delivery of multiple Nature-based Solutions co-benefits thus relies on the interplay of social, ecological, and technological systems. Achieving these outcomes requires not only robust infrastructure, innovative technology, and thriving ecosystems but also the engagement, support, and proactive management of communities and institutions, ensuring their long-term viability and effectiveness in addressing complex challenges like vector-borne diseases [18].

To build resilient urban ecosystems, it is essential to move beyond simplistic notions of cultivating or controlling nature. Instead, Nature-based Solutions must prioritize system health by fostering diverse and interconnected ecological communities [61]. Incorporating native vegetation into green spaces, such as aquatic plants and grasses, can enhance biodiversity, create habitats for natural mosquito predators, and improve overall ecosystem functioning [41]. Moreover, recreational spaces surrounding the lake could benefit from additional protection through mosquito-repelling plants, such as citronella and lemon grass [63]. Most importantly, involving communities in the design and management of these spaces ensures that Nature-based Solutions are not only biologically viable but also socially sustainable [56]. This anthropological perspective highlights the need for governance frameworks that recognize the dynamic relationships between people and their environments [58, 64]. Notably, policy and CSR enforcement play a key role in enabling and facilitating such initiatives [53, 65]. At our site visits, we found that adjacent residential and commercial developments often use the lake as a selling point for eco-friendly living. Yet, interviews revealed that developers frequently overlook building codes and drainage regulations. Enforcing CSR guidelines, strengthening regulatory frameworks, and enforcing building codes are thus critical for ensuring that ecosystem services provided by Jakkur Lake are not undermined by urban expansion.

By embracing these complexities, Nature-based Solutions can move from being isolated technical interventions to becoming integral components of urban resilience strategies. Policymakers could consider establishing funding mechanisms for a comprehensive monitoring and evaluation framework using citizen science, remote sensing, and geospatial information technologies, guiding adaptive management practices and improving intervention outcomes [66]. Thereby, a greater potential of co-benefits inherent in Nature-based Solutions may be leveraged in the case of Bengaluru. One such example is the LakeRevive tool developed by the Ashoka Trust for Research in Ecology and the

Environment (ATREE) [67]. This web-tool provides decision support on the suitability of different blue-green infrastructure types for specific locations, guidance on rejuvenation of shoreline for water quality and biodiversity enhancement, standard operating procedures, as well as an operation and maintenance manual for Nature-based Solutions at lakes.

4.3. Operationalizing WSUD for control of vector-borne diseases

The analysis of Jakkur lake highlights several critical lessons for Nature-based Solutions that relate to WSUD. We operationalized principles to match strengths, weaknesses, threats, and opportunities in Table 1. To name a few, constructed wetlands should ideally be situated at a sufficient distance from communities and beyond the flight range of key local mosquito species to minimize the risk of vector-borne diseases [68]. As previously mentioned, reducing water retention times to under 24–30 hours limits the opportunity for *Ae aegypti* larvae to complete their life cycle, while the integration of green infrastructure, such as rain gardens and permeable pavements, reduces surface runoff and prevents the formation of stagnant water (Table 1) [17]. Experts note that the retention time in wetlands like Jakkur Lake currently varies from four to eleven days, due to the size of the water body. Thus, interventions with shorter retention times are more suitable for hyperlocal scales, such as schools, science, and technology parks, as well as apartment complexes. For larger constructed wetlands, it is paramount to use plant species that have mosquito-repellent properties and to implement subsurface flow constructed wetlands, which require higher maintenance, rather than free water surface constructed wetlands. We find that these principles offer direct and indirect benefits for reducing mosquito breeding habitats.

Table 1. Urban wetland design principles, measures, and benefits for vector control

Principle	Measure	Benefit
Site-specific assessment	Collect granular data on vector breeding sites.	Tailored solutions and adaptability.
Biodiversity and ecological balance	Green urban infrastructure. Retention of shoreline vegetation, avoiding stone pitching or concretization of lake bunds.	Enhance biodiversity and natural predator-prey relationships. Maintain ecological balance within the water bodies.

Integrated rainwater drainage system	Revival and maintenance of pre-existing drainage channels. Implementation of blue infrastructure such as rain gardens, permeable pavements, and targeted aquifer recharge.	Reduced water retention and logging leading to flood risk reduction and cost savings. Water savings and aquifer replenishment.
Limited water retention time	Limit water retention time to under 24–30 hours by ensuring minimum inflows while compensating for evaporation and groundwater recharge losses.	Disrupt mosquito life cycle by preventing stagnant conditions within the lake system along with shoreline vegetation.
Water quality management Monitoring and evaluation	Regular monitoring and testing. Data collection and analysis frameworks based on citizen science and geospatial analysis.	Enable early interventions. Shared, updated knowledge and incremental improvements.
Stakeholder engagement and education	Workshops on disseminating findings from the site and baseline assessments. Community clean-up events and partnerships for stewarding hydrological ecosystems with local schools and stakeholders. Prioritize implementation activities and solutions at a local scale.	Setting realistic expectations on the outcomes of restoration projects with the communities. Foster participation and ownership. Reduce the number of containers for vector breeding.
Sustainable maintenance	Regular upkeep, vegetation management, sediment removal, and inspection of water flow.	Ensure effectiveness and sustained benefits of interventions.
Climate change adaptation	Restore and rejuvenate natural lake systems and natural water retention features, such as bioswales and constructed wetlands.	Ecosystem health. Reduce impacts of annual monsoons. Reduce urban heating.

Stakeholder engagement through, for instance, public clean-up events, is another way of seeing immediate improvements. Broad agreement exists that this is also a way of empowering local populations to take an active role in reducing mosquito breeding habitats, fostering long-term sustainability [29, 48, 62, 64]. Thus, one practical way to help local watersheds is by going into the streams, drainage areas, and adjacent natural lands to remove trash. Rainscaping provides people with a more approachable way to help their watershed by using their landscape to absorb, filter, and cool rainwater, actively improving water quality while reducing the number of unwanted breeding containers for

mosquitoes in watersheds. The fostering of native plant habitat that comes with rainscaping also helps the ecology of the watershed, as it enhances water filtration, prevents erosion, and provides habitats for mosquito predators [63]. These strategies align with ecological approaches, creating habitats that favor natural mosquito predators and disrupting vector population dynamics [22]. Regular monitoring of water quality, coupled with sustainable maintenance practices, ensures that Water Sensitive Urban Design interventions remain effective over time and do not inadvertently create new breeding grounds (Table 1) [28, 43]. For example, sediment removal and vegetation management in constructed wetlands and drainage systems prevent blockages and water stagnation, reducing the risk of unintended vector proliferation [22]. By combining WSUD principles with Sponge City strategies, Jakkur Lake may turn into a model for addressing the interconnected challenges of urban flooding, heat island effects, vector control, as well as overall ecosystem resilience [66]. These principles form the foundation for sustainable water management in dengue-endemic regions, bridging the gap between urban planning, ecosystem restoration, and public health.

5. An eco-epidemiological framework for One Health at the nexus of Nature-based Solutions and mosquito breeding in Bengaluru

The eco-epidemiological framework presented in Figure 5 distinguishes between two fundamental approaches to managing urban environmental challenges, particularly concerning vector control: the Respond paradigm and the Transform paradigm (Fig. 5) [69]. The Respond paradigm constitutes conventional, reactive strategies, primarily focusing on managing the symptoms of environmental degradation and disease outbreaks. In Bengaluru, this typically involves reactive interventions such as chemical spraying to reduce mosquito populations, which may offer temporary relief but leave the underlying ecological drivers of vector proliferation intact. Prolonged reliance on insecticides as the primary mosquito control method continues to pose severe ecological challenges, as they can disrupt ecosystems, harm non-target species, and lead to resistance in mosquito populations, necessitating alternative approaches [16, 70]. Besides, indiscriminate spraying of insecticides can come at the cost of toxic exposure to human skin and the nervous system, potentially causing rashes, swelling, and eye irritation [71]. It is found that these interventions fail to account for broader ecological and social

dynamics. While a narrow focus on symptom management may even perpetuate vulnerabilities, it also leaves urban ecosystems like Bengaluru trapped in reactive cycles of hazard management.

Figure 5. Theory of change illustrating the shift from reactive (Respond) to proactive (Transform) approaches for urban resilience through Nature-based Solutions (Based on transformative disaster risk reduction theory)

The One Health framework helps us reveal the inadequacies of this approach by emphasizing the interconnectedness of ecological, human, and animal health (Fig. 6) [53]. One Health challenges us to rethink the relationship between cities and nature, recognizing shared drivers and feedback loops that can either stabilize systems or amplify risks. For instance, mosquito distribution and abundance are significantly influenced by environmental variability, such as temperature and precipitation thresholds, which are shifting under climate change [42]. Although extensive research has examined the climate's influence on disease ecology, the complex nexus of environmental health and dengue fever dynamics, with its myriad nonlinear feedbacks, remains challenging to model and predict [7]. Additionally, the framework encompasses behavioral, socio-economic, and land-use factors, as well as cultural and spatial connectivity to natural and built environments [7, 27]. This perspective challenges the binary of built versus natural environments, urging urban planners and policymakers to embrace nature as an active partner in resilience-building.

Figure 6. The One Health framework at the nexus of urban water management and vector breeding (Based on the classic One Health Venn Diagram).

The Transform paradigm, which our perspective champions, embodies a commitment to systemic solutions that address the root causes of urban ecological imbalances and public health risks (Fig 5) [58, 62]. This approach moves beyond isolated interventions to fundamentally reshape the urban environment, aligning with the principles of Water Sensitive Urban Design and the Sponge City concept as illustrated throughout this perspective. By focusing on restoring natural hydrological processes, enhancing ecosystem services, and fostering ecological balance, the Transform paradigm aims to prevent the conditions conducive to vector breeding proactively. This involves a shift from simply eliminating mosquitoes to creating resilient urban landscapes where vector populations are naturally regulated, and the risk of disease transmission is inherently reduced [70]. Embracing the Transform paradigm, therefore,

represents a crucial step towards sustainable urban development that prioritizes the health of both human populations and the ecosystems they inhabit.

Upon identifying cost-effective intervention opportunities, this framework relies on cross-disciplinary partnerships for effective implementation. Ecologists, urban planners, public health professionals, and residents must collaborate in ensuring that interventions are not only scientifically robust but also culturally and socially resonant [62, 64]. Nature-based Solutions with a One Health approach are imperative for megacities subjected to the increasing pressures of climate change alongside excessive urban growth. We argue that policymakers can no longer afford to view green and blue spaces as luxuries or mere aesthetics. They are the foundation of systemic health, vital to human and ecological survival.

Bengaluru is just one of many cities facing annual disease outbreaks, floods, rapid urbanization, and climate extremes, necessitating a shift in both strategy and narrative toward transformative resilience [4]. Although not an isolated example, Jakkur Lake illustrates the potential of the transformative approach. Historically, a key hydrological asset in Bengaluru's network of water bodies, it now serves as an example for integrating Nature-based Solutions and Water Sensitive Urban Design to manage vector habitats while delivering co-benefits. These interventions can help stabilize microclimates, enhance biodiversity, and reconnect communities with their natural environment, creating a cascade of public health benefits [34–36]. Simultaneously, the expected benefits of Nature-based Solutions must be clearly communicated to communities at the beginning of every project, particularly with regard to criteria for Nature-based Solution successes [59]. Oftentimes the Pollution Control Board in Bengaluru measured success by whether the lake met bathing or potable water quality criteria. In the case of Jakkur Lake, this was unattainable given the catchment and environmental constraints [72]. As a result, ATREE is actively developing benchmarks for lake restoration in urban contexts, covering aspects such as water quality, hydrology, catchment characteristics, and biodiversity.

The merit of the One Health approach lies in tackling immediate risks while creating cascading benefits that ripple through urban ecosystems. Yet, the case also highlights the complexities of sustaining ecological interventions in rapidly urbanizing environments. As we found, little authoritative planning for urban expansion and high rates of migration can hinder reliable community ownership and maintenance

of a site. Governance frameworks must enable ecological integration by enforcing regulation on private real estate developers to steward surrounding ecosystems, and sustaining community engagement to ensure interventions are resilient, adaptive, and capable of addressing cyclical hazards such as dengue outbreaks [31, 32]. By embedding the principles of One Health into disaster management, the Transform paradigm not only mitigates hazards but turns them into catalysts for systemic renewal, ensuring that Nature-based Solutions constitute thriving, sustainable ecosystems.

6. Future Directions

While this perspective offers a transformative framework, the persistent lack of continuous data collection on vector dynamics, water quality, and community health outcomes at Jakkur Lake and similar sites constrains the ability to rigorously design and evaluate evidence-based strategies tailored to specific urban contexts. Thus, it is a pertinent undertaking to establish comprehensive, long-term monitoring and evaluation frameworks using a combination of citizen science, remote sensing, and geospatial information technologies to track the efficacy of Nature-based Solutions against specific vector ecology and public health outcomes. We recommend a series of field experiments to determine optimal engineering parameters for vector control, specifically: (1) the ideal distance of constructed wetlands from human communities to minimize disease risk, and (2) the required hydraulic retention time mechanisms for different vector species (ideally less than 24-30 hours to disrupt the *Aedes aegypti* life cycle) for different Water Sensitive Urban Design interventions at various scales. Future studies may further incorporate technical findings with innovative governance frameworks that successfully enforce regulation on private real estate developers to actively incorporate traditional ecological knowledge and local preferences into the co-design and maintenance of Nature-based Solutions. Further exploration of the interactions between established biocontrol measures, such as predatory fish, with new technologies such as genetically modified mosquitoes and bacteria is required for creating better, multi-pronged strategies for control and elimination of disease proliferation by mosquitoes.

7. Concluding Remarks

As cities like Bengaluru grapple with the interconnected challenges of climate variability, rapid urbanization, and recurring public health crises, it is overdue to advocate for a paradigm shift from

reactive disease control toward systemic solutions that promote environmental, human, and urban health. This approach does not merely treat the symptoms of urbanization's impact on public health but seeks to address its interconnectedness, bridging knowledge gaps and fostering resilience through ecological restoration and hydrological balance [73]. Central to this perspective is the recognition that urban ecosystems are dynamic and interconnected, requiring solutions that adapt to local contexts while embracing complexity. The case of Jakkur Lake underscores the importance of conceptualizing health holistically, acknowledging that hydrological balance, predator-prey relationships, and urban microclimates are integral to both ecological stability and human well-being. Through targeted interventions that align ecological and societal needs, Nature-based Solutions demonstrate the potential to disrupt mosquito breeding cycles while delivering co-benefits, such as enhanced biodiversity and mitigation of urban heat islands. By embedding the Sponge City concept into a One Health framework, urban landscapes can enjoy dual benefits of reduced waterlogging and mosquito proliferation, all while enhancing aquifer recharge, ecosystem services, and overall urban resilience.

However, the study also reveals critical challenges that must be addressed to scale these interventions effectively. Research gaps, particularly at the nexus of Nature-based Solutions and vector ecology, constrain the ability to design evidence-based strategies tailored to specific urban contexts. Without robust scientific evidence and long-term surveillance, the iterative refinement of these solutions remains limited [44]. Furthermore, portraying natural systems as self-sustaining often leads to underinvestment in maintenance and governance, risking the long-term viability of Nature-based Solutions. Bridging these gaps requires not only interdisciplinary collaboration but also sustained funding and political commitment to integrating One Health principles into urban water management.

In the face of mounting pressures from climate variability, rapid urbanization, and public health burdens, the One Health framework offers a blueprint for transformative action [7, 8]. Waterlogging and hydrological cycles are not isolated challenges but open up opportunities to reimagine cities as interconnected ecosystems. Through targeted investments into Nature-based Solutions based on Water Sensitive Urban Design, urban landscapes can not only mitigate the impacts of mosquito vectors but also enhance ecosystem services, support biodiversity, and foster healthier communities. Looking ahead, the key to achieving this vision lies in aligning research, policy, and practice [73]. We should take advantage

of the natural weaknesses of dengue-carrying mosquitoes, including their habitats and responses to climate variability. Combining biocontrol measures with new technologies, such as genetically modified mosquitoes and bacteria that can stop disease spread at its root, can create better ways to control, monitor, and eliminate public health burdens from dengue. The lessons from Jakkur Lake remind us that designing for balance, not just between the built and natural environments, but also between public health and ecosystem resilience, creates tools for cities to thrive amidst uncertainty.

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